

Multimetal multiligand complexes. Part-II. Equilibrium study on the formation and stability of mixed-metal, mixed-ligand complexes of cobalt-, nickel-, copper- and zinc(II) with aspartate and benzimidazole in aqueous solution

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Potentiometric study of ternary and quaternary mixtures consisting of M^{2+} ions ($M = M^1, M^2 = \text{Co, Ni, Cu and Zn}$), aspartate (A^{2-}) and benzimidazole (B) as ligands provides evidence of formation of homo- and heterobinuclear complexes: $M_2(A)_2B$, $M_2(A)_2(B-H)$, $M^1M^2(A)_2B$ and $M^1M^2(A)_2(B-H)$ involving bridging bidentate coordination by the N_1 and N_3 atoms of benzimidazole to two metal ions. (N_1H) deprotonation of bidentate coordinated bridging benzimidazole ligand in the binuclear complexes at $\text{pH} > 6$ is evident from spectral measurements. (N_1H) deprotonation constants are found to be higher with complexes of higher stability constants.

Mixed-metal mixed-ligand complexes involving more than one metal ions of the same or of different kinds may prove as suitable models for multimetal multiligand systems of biological relevance. With a view to elucidate the complexation equilibria of systems involving two different metal ions and two different ligands, we describe here the results of a combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric study on the mixed-metal mixed-ligand complex formation equilibria of M^{2+} ions ($M = \text{Co, Ni, Cu and Zn}$) with aspartate (A^{2-}) and benzimidazole (B) in binary, ternary and quaternary systems at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ in aqueous solution at a fixed ionic strength, $I = 0.1 \text{ M}$ (NaNO_3).

Results and Discussion

Protonated aspartic acid (AH_2) titrates as a triprotic acid (AH_3^+) in weakly acidic medium, the $\text{p}K^H$ values of 1.81, 3.80 and 9.59 correspond to the successive deprotonation of the two COOH groups and the NH_3^+ group¹. The aspartate dianion, A^{2-} , coordinates M^{2+} ions as a (\bar{O}, \bar{O}, N) terdentate ligand in binary and ternary complexes using the two carboxylate oxygen atoms and the amino nitrogen atom¹. In the presence of a strongly coordinating bidentate ligand, the A^{2-} ion may also provide (\bar{O}, N) bidentate coordination to Cu^{2+} , using one of the two COO^- groups and the NH_2 group to form square-planar complexes, leaving the other carboxylate group uncoordinated². Protonated benzimidazole (BH^+) titrates as a monoprotic acid ($\text{p}K^H$, 5.54). Benzimidazole (B) itself usually functions as a monodentate ligand, coordinating through the tertiary N_3 atom³. The present work is aimed at exploring the ability of benzimidazole to function as a (N_1, N_3) bridging bidentate ligand to form homo- and heterobinuclear complexes with

M^{2+} ions in the presence of aspartate as the primary ligand in aqueous solution.

Complex formation in a system of two different metal ions, M^1 and M^2 , and two different ligands A and B in aqueous solution may be described according to the equilibrium (1a),

where, the stoichiometric numbers p , q , r and s are either zero or positive integers, t is a negative integer for a protonated species, positive integer for a hydroxo or a deprotonated species and zero for a normal species⁴; charges are not shown for simplicity.

The overall stability constant (β_{pqrst}) of the complex, $M_p^1 M_q^2 A_r B_s (\text{OH})_t$ defined as

$$\beta_{pqrst} = \frac{[M_p^1 M_q^2 A_r B_s (\text{OH})_t]}{[M^1]^p [M^2]^q [A]^r [B]^s [\text{OH}]^t} \quad (1b)$$

may be used to calculate the speciation curves that provide clues to the formation equilibria of the complexes.

Binary $M^{2+} : A^{2-}$ and $M^{2+} : B$ equilibria · Complexation equilibria of the binary ($M^{2+} : A^{2-}$) and ($M^{2+} : B$) systems are found to be dominated by the following species, $M^{2+} : A^{2-}$ system: AH_3^+ , AH_2 , AH^- , A^{2-} , M^{2+} , $M(\text{OH})^+$, $M(\text{OH})_2$, $M(A)$, $M(A)_2^+$, $M(A)(\text{OH})^-$; $M^{2+} : B$ system: BH^+ , B , M^{2+} , $M(\text{OH})^+$, $M(\text{OH})_2$, $M(B)^{2+}$, $M(B)_2^+$, $M(B)(\text{OH})^+$.

Proportions of $M(\text{HA})^+$ species are found to be negligibly small in all the cases. Formation of the hydroxo

species, viz. $M(OH)^+$, $M(OH)_2$, $M(A)(OH)^-$, $M(B)(OH)^+$ have been taken into consideration in calculating the formation constants (Table 1) since the buffer regions corresponding to the metal-ligand complex formation equilibria are overlapping with the hydrolytic equilibria of the M^{2+} (aq.) ions. The ternary hydroxo complexes $M(A)(OH)^-$, and $M(B)(OH)^+$, occur with all the four M^{2+} ions ($M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn), however, the proportions of the binary hydroxo species, $M(OH)^+$ and $M(OH)_2$, are relatively higher with Zn^{2+} .

Table 1. Proton-ligand and metal-ligand binary, ternary and quaternary constants ($\log \beta_{pqrst}$) at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ in aqueous solution

Temp. = $25 \pm 1^\circ$, $I = 0.1 M$ ($NaNO_3$)

(a) Proton-ligand constants :

	<i>p</i>	<i>q</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>t</i>	$\log \beta_{00rst}$
AH_3^+	0	0	1	0	-3	15.20
AH_2	0	0	1	0	-2	13.89
AH^-	0	0	1	0	-1	9.59
BH^+	0	0	0	* 1	-1	5.54

(b) Metal-ligand binary constants :

	<i>p</i>	<i>q</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>t</i>	$\log \beta_{10rst}$			
						Co	Ni	Cu	Zn
$M(OH)^+$	1	0	0	0	1	-8.23	-8.10	-6.29	-7.89
$M(OH)_2$	1	0	0	0	2	-17.83	-16.87	-13.10	-14.92
$M(A)$	1	0	1	0	0	5.90	7.33	8.94	5.69
$M(A)_2^-$	1	0	2	0	0	9.82	12.00	15.83	9.77
$M(A)(OH)^-$	1	0	1	0	1	-3.33	-1.77	1.23	-3.20
$M(B)^{2+}$	1	0	0	1	0	2.98	3.07	3.20	2.45

(c) Metal-ligand ternary constants :

	<i>p</i>	<i>q</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>t</i>	$\log \beta_{1011t}$				
						Co	Ni	Cu	Zn	
$M(A)(B)$	1	0	1	1	0	8.94	10.11	12.02	8.78	
$M(A)(B)(OH)^-$	1	0	1	1	1	0.46	1.33	4.92	1.85	
							$\log \beta_{2021t}$			
						Co-Co	Ni-Ni	Cu-Cu	Zn-Zn	
$M_2(A)_2(B)$	2	0	2	1	0	19.33	20.41	24.47	18.63	
$M_2(A)_2(B-H)^-$	2	0	2	1	1	12.34	14.50	18.50	12.02	
			pK_{1210}^H			6.99	5.91	5.97	6.61	

(d) Metal-ligand quaternary constants :

	<i>p</i>	<i>q</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>t</i>	$\log \beta_{1121t}$			
						Co-Ni	Co-Cu	Co-Zn	
$M^1M^2(A)_2(B)$	1	1	2	1	0	20.31	23.18	19.01	
$M^1M^2(A)_2(B-H)^-$	1	1	2	1	1	13.51	15.42	12.18	
			pK_{11210}^H			6.80	7.76	6.83	
							Ni-Cu	Ni-Zn	Cu-Zn
$M^1M^2(A)_2(B)$	1	1	2	1	0	23.97	21.41	22.22	
$M^1M^2(A)_2(B-H)^-$	1	1	2	1	1	16.59	13.35	15.26	
			pK_{11210}^H			7.38	8.06	6.96	

Limits of error . ± 0.02 in log scale.

Ternary (1 : 1 : 1) and (2 : 2 : 1) $M^{2+} : A^{2-} : B$ equilibria : Mixed-ligand complexes, $M(A)(B)$ and $M(A)(B)(OH)^-$ are found to be the major species in the (1 : 1 : 1) $M^{2+} : A^{2-} : B$ systems along with the binary ones, $M(A)$ and $M(B)^{2+}$. The dominant complexation equilibria in the pH range 3–5 are

where, $M = Co, Ni, Cu$ and Zn . Rise in the concentrations of $M(A)(OH)^-$, $M(OH)_2$, B and A^{2-} with concomitant decline in the concentrations of the ternary $M(A)(B)$ complexes at $pH > 6$ gives indication of the hydrolytic equilibria (4) and (5),

Speciation of $M(A)$, BH^+ and $M_2(A)_2(B)$ in the (2 : 2 : 1) $M^{2+} : A^{2-} : B$ systems in the pH range 5.0–7.5 suggests the formation of homobinuclear $M_2(A)_2(B)$ complexes according to equilibria (6)–(8),

Contributions of equilibria (7) and (8) are found to be considerable with $M = Co, Ni$ and Zn .

The aspartate dianion (A^{2-}) provides (\bar{O}, \bar{O}, N) terdentate chelation to the M^{2+} ions in binary $M(A)$, $M(A)_2^-$ and in ternary $M(A)(B)$ complexes^{2,3}. The benzimidazole ligand (B) in the ternary $M(A)(B)$ complexes functions as a monodentate ligand, coordinating through its N_3 atom³. Simultaneous occurrence of the mononuclear ternary complexes $M(A)(B)$, and homobinuclear ternary complexes $M_2(A)_2(B)$ in the (2 : 2 : 1) $M^{2+} : A^{2-} : B$ systems and the existence of equilibria of the type (6) suggest (N_1, N_3) bridging bidentate coordination by the benzimidazole (B) ligand in these binuclear $M_2(A)_2(B)$, i.e. $(A)M(B)M(A)$ complexes (1).

Mixed-metal mixed-ligand complex formation equilibria. (1 : 1 : 2 : 1) : (M^1)²⁺ : (M^2)²⁺ : (A) : (B) systems : Speciation of $Cu(A)$, Zn^{2+} , BH^+ , AH^- and $CuZn(A)_2(B)$ in the $Cu^{2+} : Zn^{2+} : 2 A^{2-} : B$ systems indicates the formation of the heterobinuclear $CuZn(A)_2(B)$ complex according to equilibrium (9),

For the $Cu^{2+} : Ni^{2+} : 2 A^{2-} : B$ system, however, an additional equilibrium (10),

is also indicated. Small amounts of $M(A)(B)$ and $M_2(A)_2(B)$ complexes are also indicated. Analysis of the

speciation curves of the remaining systems with $M^1, M^2 = \text{Co, Ni, Cu}$ and Zn also indicates equilibria of the types (9) and (10).

Deprotonation equilibria of homo- and heterobinuclear complexes : The homo- and heterobinuclear complexes, $M_2(A)_2(B)$ and $M^1M^2(A)_2(B)$, respectively, show another buffer region at $\text{pH} > 6$ without the loss of either of the two ligands A^{2-} or B and without involving any precipitation. So the equilibria of the types (4) and (5) are less likely to occur. The only possible site of deprotonation may be the (N_1H) moiety of the bridging bidentate coordinated benzimidazole ligand in these binuclear complexes (1) according to equilibrium (11),

where, $M^1 = M^2$ for homobinuclear complexes, $M^1 \neq M^2$ for heterobinuclear complexes.

The (N_1H) deprotonation constants (K_{20210}^H and K_{11210}^H) of the $M_2(A)_2B$ and $M^1M^2(A)_2B$ complexes respectively) of bridging bidentate coordinated benzimidazole are found to be lower for Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} ions presumably because of stronger $M(d_\pi) \rightarrow B(\pi)$ interactions, due to which the electron density on the B ligand is increased, which disfavours the release of the N_1H proton. Such π -bonding is, of course, absent in the corresponding Zn^{2+} complexes. Consequently, coordinated benzimidazole in the homobinuclear Zn^{2+} complex, $\text{Zn}_2(A)_2B$, shows higher acidity relative to those with Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cu^{2+} . The benzimidazolate anion, $(B-H)^-$, may provide (N_3, N_3) bridging bidentate coordination in the $M_2(A)_2(B-H)^-$ and $M^1M^2(A)_2(B-H)^-$ complexes (2), exactly in the same manner as the imidazole residue of histidine-61 at the active site of bovine superoxide dismutase coordinates one Cu^{2+}

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ion and one Zn^{2+} ion⁵. Bridging bidentate (N_1, N_3) coordination by the imidazole ligand in binuclear $M_2(A)_2(B)$ and $M^1M^2(A)_2(B)$ complexes have earlier been established⁶ from the equilibrium study on the (1 : 1 : 1) and (2 : 2 : 1) $M^{2+} : \text{aspartate} (A^{2-}) : \text{imidazole} (B)$ systems, where, $M = (M^1) = (M^2) = \text{Co, Ni, Cu}$ and Zn . The present equilibrium study provides an evidence of formation of benzimidazole bridged homo- and heterobinuclear complex species (1, 2) in aqueous solution.

Stability constants of the binary $M(A), M(B)^{2+}$ and ternary $M(A)(B)$ complexes (Table 1) fall in the Irving-Williams order⁷ : $\text{Co}^{2+} < \text{Ni}^{2+} < \text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+}$. Overall stability constants of the heterobinuclear complexes are also found to be in the Irving-Williams order if one of the two metal

ions in the complexes is kept fixed and the other varied in the sequence $\text{Co}^{2+}, \text{Ni}^{2+}, \text{Cu}^{2+}$ to Zn^{2+} . In general, the stability constants of the binuclear (M^1-M^2) complexes ($M^1 = M^2$ and $M^1 \neq M^2$) are found to be in the general order : $\text{Cu-Cu} > \text{Cu-Ni} > \text{Cu-Co} > \text{Cu-Zn} > \text{Ni-Zn} > \text{Ni-Ni} > \text{Co-Ni} > \text{Co-Zn} > \text{Co-Co} > \text{Zn-Zn}$. Slightly higher stability of the Ni-Zn heterobinuclear complex over the corresponding Ni-Co complex may be due to slightly higher softness of the Zn^{2+} ion relative to Co^{2+} ion with regard to their bonding to the benzimidazole (B) ligand. The single $\text{Ni}(d_\pi) \rightarrow B(\pi)$ back-bonding in $\text{NiZn}(A)_2(B)$ complex adds to its stability, whereas, two opposing $\text{Ni}(d_\pi) \rightarrow B(\pi)$ bondings in the $\text{Ni}_2(A)_2(B)$ complex possibly mutually weaken each other. As a result, the stability of the Ni-Ni complex is slightly lower than that of the Ni-Zn complex. Binuclear complexes with higher values of overall stability constants (β_{20210} or β_{11210}) show higher acidity of N_1H proton of the bridging benzimidazole ligand due to $B(\sigma) \rightarrow M(\sigma)$ bonding (Table 1).

Electronic spectra of metal-ligand mixtures : The formation of binuclear complexes, $\text{Cu}_2(A)_2(B)$, $\text{CuZn}(A)_2(B)$ and the corresponding deprotonated species $\text{Cu}_2(A)_2(B-H)^-$ and $\text{CuZn}(A)_2(B-H)^-$, respectively, are also evident from electronic spectral measurements of the binary 1 : 2 $\text{Cu}^{2+} : A^{2-}$ and $\text{Cu}^{2+} : B$, ternary 1 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 : 1, $\text{Cu}^{2+} : A^{2-} : B$ and quaternary 1 : 1 : 2 : 1 $\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{Zn}^{2+} : A^{2-} : B$ mixtures at pH values corresponding to concentration maxima of $\text{Cu}(A)_2^{2-}$, $\text{Cu}(B)_2^{2+}$, $\text{Cu}(A)(B)$, $\text{Cu}_2(A)_2(B)$, $\text{Cu}_2(A)_2(B-H)^-$, $\text{CuZn}(A)_2(B)$ and $\text{CuZn}(A)_2(B-H)^-$ complexes, respectively, as determined by pH-metric study under the same experimental condition. As expected, the absorption maxima of the ternary 1 : 1 : 1 $\text{Cu}^{2+} : A^{2-} : B$ mixture occur at slightly shorter wavelength than those of the two binary 1 : 2 $\text{Cu}^{2+} : A^{2-}$ and $\text{Cu}^{2+} : B$ mixtures (Table 2). The 2 : 2 : 1 $\text{Cu}^{2+} : A^{2-} : B$ ternary mixture absorbs at a longer wavelength than the corresponding 1 : 1 : 1 mixtures, presumably because the average ligand field exerted by the bridging benzimidazole ligand (B) on two Cu^{2+} ions in the binuclear $\text{Cu}_2(A)_2(B)$ complex (1) is definitely weaker than the field exerted by the same (B) ligand when it coordinates a single Cu^{2+} ion as a monodentate ligand in the mononuclear ternary complex, $\text{Cu}(A)(B)$.

Table 2. Electronic spectral data of some binary, ternary and quaternary Cu^{2+} -ligand- Zn^{2+} mixtures in aqueous solution

$I = 0.1 M (\text{NaNO}_3)$, Temp = $25 \pm 1^\circ$

Composition	pH	Expected species	λ_{max} nm
Cu^{2+}	4.00	$\text{Cu}(\text{aq})^{2+}$	806
$\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{AH}_2$ (1 : 2)	4.10	$\text{Cu}(A)_2^{2-}$	709
$\text{Cu}^{2+} : B$ (1 : 2)	5.10	$\text{Cu}(B)_2^{2+}$	711
$\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{AH}_2 : B$ (1 : 1 : 1)	6.00	$\text{Cu}(A)(B)$	694
$\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{AH}_2 : B$ (2 : 2 : 1)	5.35	$\text{Cu}_2(A)_2(B)$	719
$\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{AH}_2 : B$ (2 : 2 : 1)	7.35	$\text{Cu}_2(A)_2(B-H)^-$	700
$\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{Zn}^{2+} : \text{AH}_2 : B$ (1 : 1 : 2 : 1)	6.35	$\text{CuZn}(A)_2(B)$	680
$\text{Cu}^{2+} : \text{Zn}^{2+} : \text{AH}_2 : B$ (1 : 1 : 2 : 1)	7.00	$\text{CuZn}(A)_2(B-H)^-$	660

N_1H deprotonation (eqm. 11) of the bridging benzimidazole (B) ligand in the binuclear $Cu_2(A)_2(B)$ and $CuZn(A)_2(B)$ complexes leaves an additional negative charge on the bridging benzimidazole (B) ligand. The resulting $(B-H)^-$ anion in the deprotonated complexes, $Cu_2(A)_2(B-H)^-$ and $CuZn(A)_2(B-H)^-$, obviously exerts a stronger ligand field than that exerted by the neutral (B) ligand. As a result, these deprotonated binuclear complexes (2) absorb at slightly shorter wavelengths. This is clearly evident from the blue-shifts in the absorption maxima by 19–20 nm (Table 2) on raising the pH of the ternary 2 : 2 : 1 $Cu^{2+} : A^{2-} : B$ mixtures (5 and 6) and the quarternary 1 : 1 : 2 : 1 $Cu^{2+} : Zn^{2+} : A^{2-} : B$ mixtures (7 and 8) above pH 6. This provides further support to the validity of the deprotonation equilibrium (11).

Experimental

All the reagents were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO_2 -free water. Metal nitrate solutions were standardized by complexometric EDTA titration methods combined with ion exchange and acid-base titrations⁸.

pH measurements were made with a Systronics 335 pH meter using a special glass electrode (accuracy ± 0.01 pH) in conjunction with a saturated calomel electrode at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ (thermostated). Spectrophotometric measurements were carried out with a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer.

Metal-ligand mixtures of the following compositions (concentration range : 10^{-2} to 10^{-3} M) in aqueous solution were prepared for the pH-metric titrations : (i) $M^{2+} : (AH_3^+ \text{ or } BH^+) = 1 : 1, 1 : 2 \text{ and } 1 : 5$ binary mixtures; (ii) $M^{2+} : AH_3^+ : BH^+ = 1 : 1 : 1$ and $2 : 2 : 1$ ternary mixtures; (iii) $(M^1)^{2+} : (M^2)^{2+} : AH_3^+ : BH^+ = 1 : 1 : 2 : 1$ quaternary mixtures; where, M, M^1 and M^2 are Co, Ni, Cu and Zn as required.

Ionic strength of all the solutions was maintained con-

stant, $I = 0.1$ M ($NaNO_3$). All the mixtures were titrated with carbonate-free 0.1 M NaOH solution⁹. Procedure for pH-metric titrations was the same as described earlier⁶. Ionic product of water (K_w) and activity coefficient of hydrogen ion under the experimental conditions were obtained from literature^{10,11}.

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand constants were calculated with the aid of SCOGS computer program⁴. Preliminary estimates of some of the binary constants supplied to the computer were calculated by the procedure of Irving and Rossotti¹² using the pH-titration curves. Computer-refined values of the constants (Table 1) corresponding to minimum standard deviation (± 0.01 ml) in the titre were used to calculate the concentration of different species required for elucidation of the complexation equilibria.

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